

Importance of dental sockets in determining trauma response, introductory dynamic response of the simplified tooth/implant model. Supplemental paper

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Abstract

In the previous paper, we had demonstrated clearly the importance of teeth socket on the remodeling capacity of bone via numerical model. In the current paper we want to demonstrate a very important issue associated with teeth. Jaw weakening is not only important for growth or bone maintenance, but also for reduction of trauma sequelae.

Keywords

Bone stiffness, PD ligaments, Numerical Simulation, Titanium dental implants, jaws weakening

Introduction

Apart from the totally different trauma response in case of implant from that occur with natural teeth model, day by day bone will increase in term of corticalization. (1) We should always remember that the attachments of the teeth to the bone will stay as it, while in the case of the implants the bone density will increase day by day reaching higher values after certain period of time. (2)

In order to evaluate the response of dentulous model and implant model to trauma response we had made this comparison based upon

- displacement evaluation
- von mises stress at the fixed region

methods

the current model is based upon the previously used model in our published paper about the resorption of the alveolar process (3) The boundaries conditions is different from the previous model as the previous model represent forces similar to those generated by mastication. But in the current model, we think that these are better representation. The boundary conditions are proposed to simulate by a fist hitting

on the mandible as in many times interpersonal violence lead to mandibular fracture by the bare hand.

Figure 1 This side is regarded as a fixed region

Figure 2 The red arrows represent the direction of the applied force

The timing of the trauma was calculating based upon the assumption it was heavy hit by the fist with high speed. Material section was the same in the model used to investigate effect of the trauma on the frontal bone response which published in the paper of ((Effect of proposed frontal bone complaint mechanism on its mechanical response as well as on the orbits)) (4)

Figure 3 This graph represents the magnitude of the force applied vs the time inside of the study

Results and discussions

The dentulous mandible reached the maximum displacement later after the implant model indicating the more potential ability of the teeth model to absorb more energy from the trauma. Implant model reached the maximum displacement after 0.02148 second, while teeth model after 0.02178 second. The maximum displacement of the teeth model was Max 6.6723e+00 mm, while that of the implant model was Max 5.9894e+00.

Faster reach to the maximum displacement in shorter time with less achieved total displacement simply mean the transfer rate of the loads are higher in case of the implant model in comparison to the teeth model.

Figure 4 Displacement of the teeth model

Figure 5 Displacement of the implants model

Displacement of the teeth model with blue boundary

Displacement Magnitude [mm]
Max 5.9894e+00
5.0000e+00
4.6000e+00
4.2000e+00
3.8000e+00
3.4000e+00
3.0000e+00
2.6000e+00
2.2000e+00
1.8000e+00
1.4000e+00
1.0000e+00
Min 0.0000e+00

Displacement Magnitude [mm]
Max 6.6723e+00
5.0000e+00
4.6000e+00
4.2000e+00
3.8000e+00
3.4000e+00
3.0000e+00
2.6000e+00
2.2000e+00
1.8000e+00
1.4000e+00
1.0000e+00
Min 0.0000e+00

Displacement of the implant model with green boundary

Figure 6 Overlapping of the implant model and the teeth model

Von Mises Stress [MPa]
Max 1.2680e+02
5.0000e+01
4.6000e+01
4.2000e+01
3.8000e+01
3.4000e+01
3.0000e+01
2.6000e+01
2.2000e+01
1.8000e+01
1.4000e+01
1.0000e+01
Min 0.0000e+00

Figure 7 Von mises stress of the teeth model

Figure 8 Von mises stress of the implant model

Figure 9 Von mises stress of the tooth model

Closer look to the model exposing the fact that the center of the teeth model is lack most of the stresses where it is concentrated at the outer regions only. This will be introduced in anew paper about the bone configuration in the mandible.

Figure 10 Von mises stress of the implant model

Figure 11 Strain of the teeth model

Figure 12 Strain of the titanium implant model

Figure 13 Teeth model strain

Figure 14 Implants model strain

Figure 15 Minor strain of the tooth model

Figure 16 Minor strain of the implant model

Figure 17 Von Mises Stress at the fixed base of the teeth model

Figure 18 Von Mises stress at the fixed base of the titanium implant model

Although the models had not yielded a significant result, they showed many differences in the patterns of the displacement and the strains. As long as the results in time is nearly identical, the model that shows more displacement is more favorable.

As a rule, all the natural structures have the lowest stiffness and highest prestress

Frequency [Hz]		Frequency [Hz]	
1	1.5554e+02	1	1.4791e+02
2	3.2492e+02	2	2.4316e+02
3	9.5334e+02	3	8.9520e+02
4	1.6296e+03	4	1.4141e+03
5	1.8660e+03	5	1.4382e+03
6	2.5845e+03	6	2.3860e+03
7	3.4825e+03	7	2.8494e+03
8	4.6900e+03	8	3.6005e+03
9	4.8518e+03	9	4.2967e+03
10	4.9012e+03	10	4.3942e+03
11	7.6414e+03	11	6.3029e+03
12	8.1438e+03	12	6.7159e+03
13	8.1983e+03	13	7.1725e+03
14	1.0418e+04	14	8.4612e+03
15	1.0828e+04	15	9.2471e+03
16	1.1542e+04	16	9.3058e+03
17	1.1970e+04	17	1.0014e+04
18	1.4316e+04	18	1.1838e+04
19	1.4942e+04	19	1.2257e+04
20	1.5967e+04	20	1.2827e+04

**Titanium
model**

**Teeth
model**

Figure 19 Eigenfrequencies of the Titanium implants model and the Teeth model

The first 20 Modes of both modes showed higher frequencies of the titanium model. Although our study represents the bone as continuous homogenous isotropic, this criterion should be held in mind.

Figure 20 Major strain of the teeth model

Figure 21 Major strain of the Titanium implants model

Major strain in each model is opposite to the other model. The presence of no tight attachment between the teeth and the alveolar process exposes the contralateral side of the bone to the most changes.

Figure 22 Minor strain of the teeth model

Figure 23 Minor strain of the titanium implant model

Same issue of the volumetric strain that make strain deeper in the model. This more involvement of the model in the strain, again, is caused by the osteointegration nature of the Titanium dental implants in contrast to the PD ligaments attachment to the teeth. This had been observed by many authors. (5)

Figure 24 strain of the Teeth model

Strain of the teeth model shows more strain away from the center. This is due to the nature of the PD ligaments of the teeth.

Figure 25 Strain of the Titanium model

Strain of the teathed model is at the periphery while in the titanium implant model is closer to the core due to the nature of the titanium implant connection to the bone, namely osseointegration.

Conclusions

Response of the bone is highly dependent upon its structure. PD ligaments present a significant weakening feature of the alveolar processes and affect both

- static response with its impact upon growth and maintenance
- dynamic response which is highly no linear with its impact upon trauma sequela.

We could assume that mandible with dental implant will have more devastating results from exposure to the trauma and the model metallic hardware will result in more devastating trauma. The current premises and conclusion will be applied to the next model of the maxilla and mandible with more relevancy to the anatomical shapes and configurations.

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.